

PROSPECTS FOR USING SOLAR UPDRAFT TOWER SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. Between 2020 and 2030, special attention is being given to the development of renewable energy sources, particularly in the solar energy sector, with plans to construct solar power plants with a total capacity of 5 GW. This article analyzes the working principle, expected benefits, and challenges. In recent decades, the Solar Updraft Tower (SUT) has been tested in hybrid systems incorporating industrial waste, geothermal energy, and biomass. However, low efficiency and high initial costs remain major barriers to the commercialization of this technology. Keywords: Solar Updraft Tower, renewable energy, solar energy, Uzbekistan, sustainable technologies.

Аннотация. В период с 2020 по 2030 годы особое внимание уделяется развитию возобновляемых источников энергии, в частности, в сфере солнечной энергетики, с планами по строительству солнечных электростанций общей мощностью 5 ГВт. данной статье анализируются принцип работы, ожидаемые преимущества и сложности. В последние десятилетия Солнечная башня восходящего потока (SUT) тестировалась в гибридных системах с использованием промышленных отходов, геотермальной энергии и биомассы. Однако низкий КПД и высокие первоначальные затраты остаются основными препятствиями для коммерциализации данной технологии. Ключевые слова: Солнечная башня восходящего потока, возобновляемая энергия, солнечная энергия, Узбекистан, устойчивые технологии.

Annotatsiya. 2020-2030 yillar oraliq'ida qayta tiklanadigan energiya manbalarini rivojlantirishga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi, ayniqsa, quyosh energiyasi sohasida 5 GVt quyosh energiyasi quvvatiga ega zavodlar qurish rejalashtirilgan. Ushbu maqolada ishlash prinsipi, kutilayotgan foyda, qiyinchiliklar tahlil qilinadi. So'nggi o'n yilliklarda SUT sanoat chiqindilari, geotermal energiya va biomassa kabi turli xil gibrid tizimlar bilan sinovdan o'tkazilgan. Biroq, past samaradorlik va yuqori boshlang'ich xarajatlar ushbu texnologiyaning tijoratlashuviga asosiy to'siq bo'lib qolmoqda. Kalit so'zlar: Quyosh Ko'tarilish Minorasi, qayta tiklanadigan energiya, quyosh energiyasi, O'zbekiston, barqaror texnologiyalar.

Introduction

The Classic Solar Updraft Tower

The most important condition for using the idea embedded in the project is the geographic location and level of solar radiation of the territory where the project is supposed to be implemented. Many regions and countries in the solar belt of the Earth, that is, in the zone approximately 35° north and south of the equator, are suitable for installing rising solar towers. As practice shows, if the annual level of solar radiation is not less than 1800 kWh/m², this fact is the basis for design. Based on this, all areas marked in orange, yellow or purple on the map in Figure 1 are suitable, including almost the entire territory of the Uzbekistan.

Fig 1 Global Irradiation Diagramm

A solar uplift tower is a large-scale renewable energy system designed to collect solar energy and convert it into electricity using a process that exploits natural thermodynamics. The system consists of three main components:

Solar collector: The first component is a large, circular solar collector, similar to a greenhouse, placed on the ground, usually made of transparent materials such as glass or plastic. This collector is designed to absorb solar radiation and convert it into heat. It acts as a huge solar "oven" that heats the air below it.

Updraft Tower: The central component of the SUT is the updraft tower itself, which is a tall cylindrical structure that can reach heights of 1,000 meters (3,280 feet) in some designs. As the solar collector heats the air below it, the air becomes less dense and rises through the tower. The updraft tower acts as a chimney for the hot air, accelerating the rise of the air due to the thermal effect.

Turbines: A series of turbines are located at the base of the tower to utilize the rapidly rising air. As the hot air rises through the tower, it passes through the turbines, causing them to spin and generate electricity. These turbines are connected to generators that convert the mechanical energy into electrical energy. (See Figure 2)

Fig 2 Classic Solar Updraft Tower Diagram

Estimates of the cost of the electricity produced range from €0.05 per kilowatt hour (kWh) to €0.25 [US\$0.07 to US\$0.34 per kWh], depending on land costs and financing. By comparison, a conventional gas-fired power plant can produce electricity for as little as €0.05/kWh. Using land for combined land use can significantly increase the financial return on this renewable energy technology, making it affordable in developing countries as a high-tech source of electricity generation.

Main Part

Agricultural use of solar upwelling towers

An important side effect of placing a large transparent membrane over a plot of land is the capture of evaporated groundwater and its return to the topsoil. This localized increase in soil moisture can make the soil beneath the collector suitable for agricultural use by effectively creating a partial greenhouse. In some cases, the land beneath the collector would not be agriculturally viable without the membrane. This means that some barren land could be returned to productive use, making this energy production strategy more economically viable and also creating agricultural capital. The clearance height below the collector allows for easy placement of farming equipment, and the collector supports can be spaced far enough apart to allow for

cultivation. Different crops can be planted depending on local soil and moisture conditions, keeping in mind that the area near the center will have too much airflow to support plant growth.

Using a Solar Updraft Tower to Generate Electricity together with Solar Panels

Other solar technologies, such as collectors that use solar radiation to convert water into steam, or photovoltaic (PV) arrays, generate significant excess heat. In the case of PV, high temperatures reduce their power generation capacity. Using a solar updraft tower in combination with solar collectors or PV arrays can improve the efficiency of both systems. The constant flow of wind can cool the collectors with air, while increasing the energy output per unit area of land used, making a solar updraft tower a more efficient proposition. What must be considered in terms of the efficiency of combining these systems is the loss of some direct solar radiation as a result of its deflection by the membrane and the amount of cooling that can ideally be achieved. (See Figure 4)

Fig 4: Co-generation Solar Updraft Tower

This strategy can also be combined with agricultural uses, where solar collectors or PV arrays would be placed at the center of the collector, where the winds are too strong for plant growth.

Optimization

The electricity produced by a solar updraft tower is proportional to the global solar radiation intensity, the collector area, and the tower height. In reality, there is no optimal physical size for such plants. Optimal sizes can only be calculated by incorporating the specific component costs (collector, column, turbines) for individual sites. Thus, plants with different optimal key sizes will be built for different sites, but always at an optimal price: if the collector area is cheap and concrete is expensive, then the collector will be large and the tower relatively small, and if the land for the collector is expensive, then its area will be smaller but the tower will be taller.

For a quick overview, typical sizes for selected solar updraft tower capacities are given in Table 1. These figures are based on typical material and construction costs

Table 1. Typical sizes of SUT and power generation

Power		50MBT	100MBT	200MBT
Tower height	M	750	1000	1000
Tower diameter	M	90	110	120

Collector diameter	м	3750	4300	7000
Amount of electricity with solar radiation 2300 kWh/m2+	гВтчас/а	153	320	680
Amount of electricity with solar radiation 1800 kWh/m2++	гВтчас/а	120	250	532

+For areas with increased solar radiation zone (upper limit)

++ For areas with decreased solar radiation zone (lower limit of profitability)

General advantages of the SUT system

1. The collector can use all solar radiation, both direct and diffuse. This is very important for tropical countries, where the sky is often cloudy.

2. Because the soil under the collector works as a natural heat storage system, solar updraft towers will operate 24 hours on clean solar energy, with reduced power at night.

3. Solar rising towers are particularly reliable. The turbines and generators - provided there is a constant air flow - are the only moving parts of the plant.

4. Unlike conventional power plants, solar towers do not require cooling water. This is an advantage in many sunny countries that already have serious water supply problems.

Conclusion

The solar updraft tower represents an innovation in renewable energy technology. By harnessing solar radiation and natural air movement, it has the potential to provide clean, reliable, and scalable energy to the world’s growing population. Although the technology has some challenges, its benefits in terms of sustainability and low environmental impact make it an attractive solution in the search for greener energy sources. Most importantly, the positive quality of the SUT is its resilience to climate change. This is especially noticeable when comparing the SUT to the operation of a wind turbine.

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